

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

International Journal of Hydrogen Energy

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/he

Parametric investigation and multi-objective optimization of building-integrated hybrid energy storage system with metal hydride tank

Nikolaos Ziozas^{a,*}, Petros Iliadis^{a,b}, Evangelos Bellos^{a,c}, Angeliki Kitsopoulou^a, Renos Rotas^a, Dimitra Gonidaki^{a,c}, Nikolaos Nikolopoulos^a

^a Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH), Chemical Process and Energy Resources Institute (CPERI), Aigialeias 52, 15125, Marousi, Greece

^b Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering of Democritus University of Thrace, Xanthi, 67100, Greece

^c Department of Mechanical Engineering, School of Engineering, University of West Attica, 250 Thivon & Petrou Ralli, 12244, Athens, Greece

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Hydrogen storage
Metal hydride
Hybrid storage
Photovoltaics
Optimization

ABSTRACT

The present analysis investigates a hybrid energy storage system consisting of lead-acid batteries and a hydrogen storage tank using metal hydrides. A dynamic simulation is conducted for a 1000 m² building, supported by photovoltaics and a hybrid storage system to meet annual appliance and lighting demands. The research focuses on optimal system sizing to minimize both grid electricity demand and total capital costs. Multi-objective optimization was conducted through a Dymola–Python NSGA-II algorithm interface, while energy simulations utilized the INTEMA building tool. Results indicate an optimal solution with 118 lead-acid batteries (339.84 kWh) and a 4 kg H₂ capacity of a metal hydride storage tank, achieving 99.2 % grid autonomy. Although the 40 kW and 50 kW PV systems achieve comparable energy autonomy (98 %), their total cost is doubled compared to the optimal solution due to increased demanded MH tank capacity (60 kg H₂) to support the battery system, outperforming the total cost.

1. Introduction

The ongoing energy transition due to the climate and energy crisis poses the challenge for a rapid diffusion and integration of clean and sustainable energy technologies in every domain of our society [1]. This increasing global demand for renewable and decarbonised energy sources has led to significant advancements in hybrid renewable energy systems (HRES) [2]. Hybrid renewable energy systems combine numerous renewable energy technologies such as solar, wind, and hydro, providing a promising solution to the grid dependency and intermittency issues of conventional renewable energy systems [3,4]. The reliability and consistency of their energy supply make them attractive alternatives for both urban and remote applications.

Among the multiple components of HRES, the stability and efficiency of energy supply relies on the integration and optimum design of energy storage systems through the effective utilization of RES. The most common energy storage methods, such as chemical batteries and pumped hydro storage, present numerous limitations, including environmental impact, efficiency losses, and scalability issues. For this reason, hybrid energy storage systems have been proposed with hydrogen to be

the most efficient and sustainable storage solution [5]. The emergence of hydrogen as a sustainable energy storage solution reflects the urgent need to address the renewable energy technologies challenge due to intermittency and uncertainty [6]. In this direction, proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFC) provide a satisfying electrical efficiency of around 30 %–60 % by utilizing compressed hydrogen as input [5,7]. However, the existing compressed hydrogen storage solutions limit their use in large-scale projects in the building sector and demand a high profile of respective pressures of the associated gas and liquid media [8].

A promising hydrogen storage solution to address this challenge is the metal hydride tank (MHT) that can reversibly desorb and adsorb hydrogen, with the advantage of low-pressure and high-volume storage density conditions. Depending on the MH alloy, the storage density can reach the value of 100 kg/m³, providing flexibility on the scale and scope of hydrogen storage applications [5]. Metal hydride storage tanks integrated into HRES can address some of the key challenges associated with renewable energy storage, such as energy density and durability [9]. Furthermore, this coupling of MHTs in HRES allows the efficient storage and release of hydrogen, which can be used to generate electricity through fuel cells or internal combustion engines during periods

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: n.ziozas@certh.gr (N. Ziozas).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2025.04.522>

Received 11 March 2025; Received in revised form 25 April 2025; Accepted 29 April 2025

Available online 24 May 2025

0360-3199/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of Hydrogen Energy Publications LLC. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

of low renewable energy production [10]. This feature improves the overall efficiency of the HRES and provides a buffer against the variability and intermittency of renewable energy sources. Metal hydrides have been extensively studied for their applications in hydrogen storage, fuel cells, and thermal management systems.

Thus, it is crucial to investigate the advantages of the integration and optimum design of MHTs in HRES. "MH tanks present a significant advantage in terms of high volumetric energy density compared to conventional hydrogen storage methods, enabling more compact storage solutions [11]. However, the gravimetric energy density of MH tanks is generally lower than that of compressed gas or liquid hydrogen storage. This limitation is primarily due to the inherent weight of the metal hydride materials required for hydrogen absorption. Nevertheless, the moderate operating pressures and low-temperature requirements of many MH alloys make them ideal for stationary or integrated renewable energy applications, where volumetric efficiency, safety, and system integration are prioritized over portability and gravimetric density [12]. On the other hand, it has been observed that in some applications, such as forklifts, MH tanks could have a dual purpose, utilizing weight as a counterbalance to enhance forklifts' functionality without adding redundant mass [13]. Nevertheless, a few challenges are raised associated with the integration of MH tanks in HRES, such as the capital and operational cost of its components and the need for advanced control systems to manage the thermal and pressure operating conditions.

MH tanks function through reversible chemical reactions between hydrogen and metal alloys at low temperatures and pressures compared to a typical compressed hydrogen storage tank. Thus, the respective desorption and absorption of hydrogen in the MH tank represent endothermic and exothermic reactions respectively. The endothermic reaction during the discharging process requires an amount of heat that is usually supplied by the connected PEMFC depending on the requested fuel cell's power output. Respectively, there is a need to remove the heat from the MH tank, which is an outcome of the exothermic reaction of the charging process [14]. Based on the study by Davids et al., optimizing the heat transfer from the PEMFC to the MH tank is necessary, as the heat source at ambient air temperature levels is not sufficient for the respective requirements of a PEMFC [15]. The most common solutions so far for heat exchange optimization are the integration of fins in the MH tank, the addition of a heat exchanger, and phase change materials during the discharging process [5]. From another point of view, Gambini et al. [16] studied a variety of high and low-temperature alloys (i.e., Mg₂Ni, LaNi₅, etc.) through mathematical modelling and simulation. They found that the preference for the used alloy is based on its encumbrance and reaction time, which is favourable for low-temperature alloys as their reaction temperature provides flexibility for large-scale applications. However, Song et al. [17] have shown that the wasted heat from a PEMFC can meet an MH tank's requirements for hydrogen desorption in the PEMFC–MH system. In terms of the heat transfer efficiency in the PEMFC–MH system, the water-cooled ones have been proven to be more efficient than the respective air-cooled systems, while the integration of heat pipes in the MH tank can further improve the efficiency of the discharging process [18]. Similarly, other thermal management technologies, beyond the use of fins and phase change materials (PCMs), are the straight and spiral tube configurations [19]. The Integration of tube designs in the hydride material leads to a reduction of thermal gradients by distributing heat exchange fluid effectively. Specifically, Mellouli et al. [19] showcase that the spiral-type heat exchanger, through an experimental set-up, reduces the charge/discharge times of the reactor. Wang et al. [20] propose a novel radiation mini-channel reactor (RMCR) to improve thermal efficiency and an RMCR with a jacket to eliminate the unfavorable heat transfer regions inside RMCR. The results indicate that the RMCR shows the best performance saving up to 77 %, 52 %, and 37 % reaction time than no heat exchange tube (tank reactor), straight tube and spiral tube, respectively [20]. Kaplan [21] investigates the effects of heat transfer mechanisms on the charging process in three different cylindrical

reactors with the same base dimensions, namely a closed cylinder cooled with natural convection, circular fins have been integrated into the second reactor and a third reactor cooled with water circulating around the bed by means of a water pump. The third reactor presents the best results in terms of linearity of the temperatures and charging time due to the exothermic nature of the hydrogen absorption [21]. Another interesting work by Di Giorgio et al. [22] shows that an HSES of an MH tank and lithium-ion battery pack integrated into a plug-in fuel cell electric scooter is effectively capable of passively controlling the temperature of the battery pack while enhancing at the same time the on-board storage energy density. Following the same research field on MH tanks, Di Giorgio et al. [23] examined a fuel cell electric bicycle prototype, showing that the HESS prevents battery degradation and improves safety while achieving 19 % and 167 % higher gravimetric and volumetric energy densities than the battery pack of the original e-bike.

Nevertheless, the most challenging obstacle for the MH tanks is the optimization of the desorption process to meet the required load demand of the connected PEMFC due to hysteresis in the heat transfer process [5]. For this reason, the scientific community in this field has expressed interest in researching this system's thermal management. For instance, Cho et al. [24] utilized the PID method in a PEMFC–MH system to minimize the error at the actual and required hydrogen desorption rate. Similarly, Cavo et al. [25] used a variable opening valve for the wasted heat to control the MH tank temperature.

The previous literature review shows that there is a great interest in the energy storage system for achieving sustainable buildings. The present work investigates an innovative hybrid energy storage system coupled with photovoltaics to cover the basic electrical needs (appliances and lighting) of a building with a floor area of 1000 m². The storage unit includes batteries and a hydrogen tank, with the battery being responsible for short-term storage, while the tank is for long-term storage (seasonal). The novelty of this work is based on the use of an innovative tank with metal hydrates, optimizing the total system with a multi-objective optimization procedure and using advanced control techniques for selecting the proper storage strategy. The optimization is based on the application of evolutionary algorithms and aims i) to minimize the total capital cost of the system and ii) to minimize the electricity demand by the grid. The analysis also includes a detailed parametric investigation, and finally, interesting conclusions can be extracted for the design boundaries of systems like the present one. The dynamic investigation is conducted with the INTEMA.building tool which is based on the Modelica programming language, and it can simulate with high accuracy the dynamic phenomena, as well as apply the proper control strategies for the examined unit.

2. Material and methods

The present section introduces the examined hybrid renewable energy system (HRES), followed by the respective Dymola-based component models. The mathematical foundation of each component and the methodology for investigating and optimizing the HRES are also given.

2.1. Description of the studied system

The examined system concerns the design of an HRES model consisting of photovoltaic panels and an integrated hybrid storage system consisting of a battery system and a compact hydrogen storage system that will cover the electrical load of a fictional residential or commercial building. The building is located in the city of Athens with a conditioning area of 1000 m². The developed model focuses on the innovative hydrogen storage system that will fit in a 20-foot prototype container and consists of an electrolyzer, a metal hydride tank, a PEM fuel cell, and associated controllers for the optimum energy management of each component. Specifically, the hydrogen storage system has been modeled based on the technical characteristics of the GKN Hydrogen (i.e., model HY2MEDI) [26] to produce hydrogen through electrolysis, store it in an

innovative metal hydride storage tank, and then reconvert it to electrical and thermal energy. Moreover, the system utilizes the surplus of integrated PV panels of 440 W each on the building’s roof through an auxiliary battery subsystem of 2.88 kWh for each battery and a smart controller for an energy-efficient function of the system (i.e., the synergy of the battery system and the electrolyzer for the demanded hydrogen production). The electrolysis system is based on 10 modules of electrolyzers designed by Enapter (AEM Electrolyser EL 4.1) [27] with a nominal output of 2.4 kW each, while two identical modules of proton-exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cells are used to provide an overall output of 16 kW.

All the examined components and subsystems were modeled and simulated in the Dymola environment. Each component was modeled in the Modelica language and tested to validate the requested nominal capacities and outputs based on the manufacturers’ specifications. Each component and the respective control system will be further analyzed below, while the outline of the whole model is depicted in Fig. 1.

A typical electrical load for the demo building of a total area of 1000 m² was utilized, demanding a yearly electrical load of 53,592 kWh. Specifically, the electrical load includes the used electrical appliances and the total lighting loads with the respective parameters and a typical daily operating profile (see Fig. S1 in the Supplementary Material) of the building, as shown in Table 1. Specifically, the examined electrical appliances concern typical residential appliances, excluding any heating and cooling electrical appliances. In Table 2, the main parameters of the simulated hydrogen storage system are summarized according to the nominal values extracted from the GKN Hydrogen manufacturer of the HY2MEDI model [25].

PV panels are used to cover the building’s electrical load. The integration of a large amount of PV panels allows the metal hydride tank and the batteries to be fully functional. For this reason, a controller was designed to check every hour if there is a surplus or deficit of power between the demanded electrical load and the produced power from the PV panels. In case a surplus of power is detected, the controller first gives priority to the battery system, then to the electrolyzer, and finally to the grid. The battery system has a minimum state of charge (SOC) at 10 % and a respective maximum SOC of 100 %. If the batteries are full, then the control system checks the storage capacity of the metal hydride tank, and if it is not full, it activates the electrolysis process on the electrolyzer

Table 1
Operating parameters of the examined building.

Parameter	Value
Specific lighting electrical load [W/m ²]	5
Mean operating fraction of the lighting [%]	40
Specific appliances’ electrical load [W/m ²]	10
Mean operating fraction of the appliances [%]	40
Total floor area [m ²]	1000

Table 2
Main parameters for the involved components of the hydrogen storage system model.

Parameters	Values
Electrolyzer nominal electricity input [kW]	24
Electrolyzer nominal efficiency [%]	60
PEM fuel cell nominal electricity output in [kW]	16
PEM fuel cell nominal efficiency [%]	50
Hydrogen storage system pressure level [bar]	35
Volume density storage [m ³ /kWh]	0.0037
Volume density storage [kWh/m ³]	267
Operating temperature [°C]	20–60 °C
Absorption/Desorption rate	>99 %
Battery system - minimum state of charge (SOC) in [%]	10 %
Battery system - maximum state of charge (SOC) in [%]	100 %

to charge it with purified hydrogen. The produced hydrogen is dried in the hydrogen dryer of 0.2 kW power consumption and checked for the required quality in the gas analysis. Only hydrogen of the required quality is used further.

On the other hand, if the electricity produced by the PV panels cannot cover the building’s demanded electrical load, a deficit of electricity is detected on the controller. Then, the control system prioritizes the batteries and manages to cover the deficit from them; if not, the PEM fuel cell is activated. However, another condition concerning the available H₂ on the metal hydride tank is checked. If the tank’s SOC is above 10 %, then two identical PEM fuel cells are activated to cover the demanded load with a maximum output of 16 kW. The power range of the fuel cells is controlled in the 30 %–100 % range, which corresponds to an output of 2.4–16 kW. Each module is linked to a heat management

Fig. 1. The outline of the HRES with hydrogen storage in the Dymola environment.

system, where the associated heat exchangers release the wasted heat. Finally, the grid will cover the electrical load if both the batteries and metal hydride tank are below 10 % SOC. Thus, to increase the energy autonomy and efficiency of the hydrogen storage system, the components were dimensioned according to the consumption/production patterns after a detailed hourly-based simulation for a year in real weather data. Therefore, it is worth examining each focal component (i. e., electrolyzer, metal hydraulic tank, and PEM fuel cell) separately to understand the operational flow of the present model fully. The following modeling of the examined components will focus on the thermal behavior and adaptability of the real ones based on each manufacturer’s specifications.

2.2. Electrolyzer modeling

A PEM electrolysis (i.e., electrolyzer) model was developed using Modelica language and the INTEMA building tool to simulate hydrogen production. According to the developed model, the electrolyzer is fed with water m_{H_2O} of temperature equal to the temperature of the PEM, T_{PEM} , which is normally equal to 80 °C [28]. The execution of the electrochemical reaction of hydrogen production requires an electricity rate input, P_{el} . In addition, the area of the proton exchange membrane of each cell (A_{cell}) and the number of the total cells of the electrolyzer are inserted as a parameter. Finally, the hydrogen’s lower heating value equals 120 MJ/kg [29].

This electrolyzer model produces hydrogen at a pressure of 35 bar and is, therefore, perfectly matched to the properties of the metal hydride tank. The overall hydrogen storage modeled system uses ten identical electrolysis modules to reduce the probability of a system failure in the event of a malfunction during electrolysis operation. Each module has a nominal output of 2.4 kW. The absorbed power can be reduced to up to 60 % of this value when producing hydrogen. In total, the absorbed power in electrolysis mode can, therefore, be regulated from 1.44 to 24.0 kW. Below, an analysis of the theoretical foundation of the modeled electrolyzer is provided.

The theoretical energy demand for the PEM electrolysis of water is the total energy demand without any losses, and it can be calculated as:

$$\Delta H = \Delta G + T \cdot \Delta G \quad (1)$$

Where ΔG is the electrical energy demand (change in Gibb’s free energy), and $T \cdot \Delta G$ is the thermal energy demand. The total energy demand of the water splitting can be correlated to the thermoneutral cell voltage, U_{tn} , accordingly [30]:

$$U_{tn} = \frac{\Delta H}{2 \cdot F} \quad (2)$$

Which is calculated at 1.473 V for the temperature range, around 80 °C, of the specific electrochemical reaction. The generated heat thermal losses (Q_{heat}) of the water electrolysis can be calculated as:

$$Q_{heat} = n_{cell} \cdot (V - U_{tn}) \cdot J \cdot A_{pem} \quad (3)$$

where V [V] is the potential of the electrolyzer, J , is the current density [A/m^2], A_{PEM} is the area of the membrane [m^2], and n_{cell} stands for the number of series-connected electrolytic cells, which is equal to 1 in the present analysis.

According to the methodology of Ni et al. [31] about the PEM operation, the electrical input, $P_{electrical}$, required for the electrochemical model is calculated in Watts as:

$$P_{electrical} = n_{cell} \cdot I \cdot V \quad (4)$$

The current, I , is usually calculated by using the current density, J , and the area of the cell, A_{cell} :

$$I = J \cdot A_{cell} \quad (5)$$

Following, as V , is denoted the potential of the cell calculated in

Volts, and it is determined as:

$$V = V_o + V_{ohm} + V_{act_{an}} + V_{act_c} \quad (6)$$

Where V_o [V] is the reversible potential, which is calculated according to the Nernst equation [32]:

$$V_o = 1.229 - 8.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot (T_{PEM} - 298.15) \quad (7)$$

T_{PEM} is denoted as the temperature of the proton exchange membrane, and 298.15 K is the reference temperature of the environment. The ohmic overpotential, V_{ohm} , is calculated as:

$$V_{ohm} = R_{PEM} \cdot J \cdot A_{PEM} \quad (8)$$

The ohmic resistance, R_{PEM} , is the resistance that the proton exchange membrane presents against the hydrogen ions that transport through it. It is a function of the presence of water, which is denoted as $\lambda(x)$, the membrane’s thickness, L , and the membrane’s temperature T_{PEM} [28]. More specifically, the humidification degree is a function of the membrane’s depth (x), with the depth being equal to zero on the cathode’s side and maximum on the anode’s side.

$$\lambda(x) = \frac{\lambda_a - \lambda_c}{L} \cdot x + \lambda_c \quad (9)$$

Where λ_a and λ_c are the water contents at the anode and cathode membrane interface, respectively. These values are dimensionless and considered to be equal to 14 for the anode and 10 for the cathode [28]. The local ionic conductivity $\sigma[\lambda(x)]$ is empirically calculated according to the following equation [33]:

$$\sigma[\lambda(x)] = (0.5139 \cdot \lambda(x) - 0.326) \cdot e^{\left(1268 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{303} - \frac{1}{T_{PEM}}\right)\right)} \quad (10)$$

Therefore, the ohmic resistance is determined as:

$$R_{PEM} = \int_0^L \frac{dx}{\sigma[\lambda(x)]} \quad (11)$$

This expression can be simplified to the following analytical solution:

$$R_{PEM} = e^{-\left(1268 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{303} - \frac{1}{T_{PEM}}\right)\right)} \cdot \frac{L}{\lambda_a - \lambda_c} \cdot \frac{1}{0.5139} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{\lambda_a - 0.634365}{\lambda_c - 0.634365} \right) \quad (12)$$

The activation overpotential of the anode and cathode of the electrode can be expressed as:

$$V_{act_a} = \frac{R \cdot T_{PEM}}{F} \cdot \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{J}{2 \cdot J_{o_a}} \right) \quad (13)$$

$$V_{act_c} = \frac{R \cdot T_{PEM}}{F} \cdot \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{J}{2 \cdot J_{o_c}} \right) \quad (14)$$

Where R is the gas constant equal to 8.314 J/mol•K, F is the Faraday constant equal to 94,485 s A/mol, and J_o is the exchange current density that for the anode is considered equal to $10^{-5} A/m^2$, whereas for the cathode is equal to $10 A/m^2$ [28].

The inlet flow rate of water is a known variable, whereas the outlet flow rate [kg/s] of the oxygen, hydrogen, and water that is not electrolyzed can be determined as [28]:

$$\dot{m}_{H_2} = M_{H_2} \cdot \frac{J}{2F} \quad (15)$$

$$\dot{m}_{O_2} = M_{O_2} \cdot \frac{J}{4F} \quad (16)$$

$$\dot{m}_{H_2O,reacted} = M_{H_2O} \cdot \frac{J}{2F} \quad (17)$$

Where M_{H_2} , M_{O_2} , and M_{H_2O} are the molar masses of H_2 , O_2 , and H_2O and

are considered equal to $M_{H_2} = 0.002$ kg/mol, $M_{O_2} = 0.032$ kg/mol, and $M_{H_2O} = 0.018$ kg/mol. Therefore, the power of the produced fuel Q_{fuel} [W] is calculated as:

$$Q_{fuel} = \dot{m}_{H_2} \cdot LHV \quad (18)$$

Where LHV is the lower heating value of the hydrogen. The energy efficiency of the electrolyzer can be determined as:

$$\eta_{en} = \frac{Q_{fuel}}{P_{el}} \quad (19)$$

A validation procedure has been conducted to verify the calculations of the present model. More specifically, a wide range of current density (J) values has been studied, and the corresponding cell potential (V) values have been calculated. The calculations extracted from the developed model are compared with the respective calculations of the study of Ioroi et al. [34]. Fig. S2 in the Supplementary Material illustrates the results for the present and reference studies, as well as the degree of percentage deviation between them. The deviation of the developed model ranges between 1.87 % and 4.60 %.

2.3. Proton-exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) modeling

A fuel cell is an electrochemical device in which chemical energy is directly converted into electrical energy and heat through an electrochemical reaction of hydrogen fuel with oxygen [35,36]. It consists of an electrolyte in contact with an anode (negative electrode) and a cathode (positive electrode). Fuel cells are classified according to their electrolyte materials and fuels [37]. They are different in their power outputs, operating temperatures, electrical efficiencies, and typical applications. A typical PEM fuel cell has the following reactions:

In the present research, a typical PEM fuel cell is modeled based on the following theoretical background's fundamental electrochemical process and thermal behavior. As we mentioned in the previous sections, the PEM model will cover the electrical load when there is a surplus of power in the system and the batteries cannot fully support it. Then, the fuel cell uses the reaction between hydrogen and atmospheric oxygen to generate electricity at low overpressures, resulting in the reaction exhaust air (moist) being blown off into the environment. A pressure buffer prevents the pressure from dropping too much when the fuel cell starts up, as the waste heat required for the storage tank is not immediately available. Two identical modules are used to provide the required output (up to 16 kW) with an overall efficiency of 50 %.

The PEM electrochemical process concerns the transfer of electrons between an electrode and the electrolyte with a change in Gibbs free energy. At the standard condition (25 °C, 1 atm), Gibbs free energy (ΔG) corresponds to the maximum electrical total work of the fuel cell (FC) $W_{max,fc}$ [37]:

$$W_{max,fc} = -\Delta G \quad (20)$$

Thus, the open circuit voltage or the theoretical voltage of the cell is given by the following equation [38]:

$$E_o = \frac{-\Delta G}{nF} = 1.230 \cdot V \quad (21)$$

where, n, is the number of electrons released (i.e., $n = 2$, for all the hydrogen FCs as for each mole of hydrogen, 2 mol of the electron are released) and F is Faraday's constant, which corresponds to the total electrical charge of 1 mol of the electron. At the non-standard condition, Gibbs free energy will occur reversible changes, which are related to the partial pressure of reactants and products. This corresponding voltage

can be determined by the Nernst equation [39], as follows:

$$V_{Nernst} = E_o + \frac{RT_{fc}}{nF} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{P_{H_2,an} \cdot \sqrt{P_{O_2,ca}}}{P_{H_2O,an}} \right) \quad (22)$$

where R is the ideal gas constant ($R = 8.314$ J/mol•K), T_{fc} is the PEM fuel cell's operating temperature in Kelvin, and $P_{H_2,an}$, $P_{O_2,ca}$ and $P_{H_2O,an}$ (atm) are the partial pressures of hydrogen, oxygen, and water respectively. The effective partial pressures are given by the following equations:

$$P_{H_2,an} = 0.5 \cdot P_{H_2O,an} \cdot \left[\frac{1}{e^{\frac{1.653i}{T_{fc}^{1.334}} \cdot x_{H_2O}}} - 1 \right] \quad (23)$$

$$P_{O_2,ca} = P \cdot \left[1 - x_{H_2O} - x_{N_2}^{channel} \cdot e^{\frac{0.291 \cdot i}{T_{fc}^{0.832}}} \right] \quad (24)$$

where x_{H_2O} is the molar fraction of water, x_{N_2} is the molar fraction of nitrogen in the air stream and, i, is the current density of the PEM fuel cell. The current density is considered constant, while the remaining parameters could be given by Ref. [40]:

$$\begin{aligned} \log(P_{H_2O,an}) = & -2.1794 + 0.02253 \cdot (T_{fc} - 273.15) \\ & - 9.1837 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot (T_{fc} - 273.15)^2 \\ & + 1.4454 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot (T_{fc} - 273.15)^3 \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

$$x_{H_2O} = \frac{P_{H_2O,an}}{P} \quad (26)$$

$$x_{N_2}^{channel} = \frac{x_{N_2,in} - x_{N_2,out}}{\ln \left(\frac{x_{N_2,in}}{x_{N_2,out}} \right)} \quad (27)$$

$$x_{N_2,in} = 0.79 \cdot (1 - x_{H_2O}) \quad (28)$$

$$x_{N_2,out} = \frac{1 - x_{H_2O}}{1 + \left(\frac{0.21}{0.79} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda_{air} - 1}{\lambda_{air}} \right)} \quad (29)$$

where λ_{air} is the stoichiometric air ratio.

The irreversible electrochemical processes produce three types of voltage losses such as Ohmic V_{ohm} , activation V_{act} , and concentration V_{con} losses. Thus, the voltage output of a typical PEM fuel cell for the N_{cell} number of cells is given by the following equation [37]:

$$V_{fc} = V_{Nernst} - (V_{act} + V_{ohm} + V_{con}) \quad (30)$$

The polarization curve is based on equation (10), showcasing the influence of each voltage loss from low to high current density. The activation losses are the energy that reactants must overcome in the chemical reaction and take place at each electrode-electrolyte interface. These potential losses have a high impact on the output voltage at low currents, and they are calculated by the following expression [36,41]:

$$V_{act} = -(\xi_1 + \xi_2 \cdot T_{fc} + \xi_3 \cdot T_{fc} \cdot \ln(C_{O_2}) + \xi_4 \cdot T_{fc} \cdot \ln(I)) \quad (31)$$

$$\xi_1 = -0.948 \quad (32)$$

$$\xi_2 = 0.00286 + 0.0002 \cdot \ln(A_{fc}) + 4.38 \cdot 10^5 \cdot \ln(C_{H_2}) \quad (33)$$

$$\xi_3 = 7.6 \cdot 10^5 \quad (34)$$

$$\xi_4 = -1.93 \cdot 10^{-4} \quad (35)$$

$$I = i \cdot A_{fc} \quad (36)$$

$$C_{O_2} = 1.97 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot P_{O_2} \cdot e^{\left(\frac{498}{T_{fc}}\right)} \quad (37)$$

$$C_{H_2} = 9.174 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot P_{H_2} \cdot e^{\left(\frac{-77}{T_{fc}}\right)} \quad (38)$$

In the above equations, ξ_i indicates the parametric coefficients, A_{fc} (cm^2) is the active surface area, C_{O_2} and C_{H_2} are the oxygen and hydrogen concentrations, and I is the cell current. Respectively, the Ohmic losses occur due to the electrical and ionic resistance from the flow of ions and electrons through different materials (i.e., electrolytes, collector plates, and graphite electrodes). Based on Ohm's law, the ohmic losses can be calculated by the following equations [42]:

$$V_{ohm} = I \cdot (R_m - R_c) \quad (39)$$

$$R_m = \frac{r_{mem} \cdot L}{A_{fc}} \quad (40)$$

$$r_{mem} = 181.6 \cdot \left(\frac{1 + 0.03 \cdot i + 0.062 \cdot \left(\frac{T_{fc}}{303}\right)^2 \cdot i^{2.5}}{(\Psi - 0.634 - 3 \cdot i) \cdot e^{4.18 \cdot \left(\frac{T_{fc} - 303}{T_{fc}}\right)}} \right) \quad (41)$$

where R_m is the membrane resistance, R_c is the resistance of the constant part of the cell ($R_c = 0.0001-0.0005$), r_{mem} is the specific membrane resistance, L is the membrane thickness, and Ψ is an empirical factor that corresponds to the membrane hydration ($\Psi = 14$ – fully hydrated, $\Psi = 23$ – fully saturated) [36]. Finally, concentration losses occur due to the diffusion of reactants and products between the bulk flow and the reaction site, and it is applied at the region of low current. Thus, it is considered the loss of the remaining reactants that have not been used and is given by:

$$V_{con} = \frac{RT_{fc}}{nF} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{i_L}{i_L - i}\right) \quad (42)$$

where i_L is the maximum current density.

Thus, a typical electrochemical and thermal PEM fuel cell model was developed by applying the above equations to the Dymola environment written in Modelica language. The polarization curve of the present Dymola model is depicted in Fig. 2.

For validation purposes, the present PEMFC model was compared to the extensive works on PEMFC models from Marandi et al. [36] (i.e., Reference study A) and Ahmadi et al. [35] (i.e., Reference study B), as

Fig. 2. PEMFC Voltage output of the examined model and the deviation of the present model from the reference studies (A) [20] and (B) [35].

shown in the polarization curve in Fig. 2. All models have been simulated under the assumptions [36].

- The models operate at steady state conditions, and chemical reactions reach an equilibrium state.
- The operating pressure is 3 atm, and the pressure change throughout the PEM is ignored.
- The temperature is distributed uniformly across the fuel stack.
- The incoming air to the fuel cell consists of 79 % N_2 and 21 % O_2 .

Based on these assumptions and operating parameters, all models' output voltage follows the same distribution. The present model successfully simulated the PEM fuel cell model, presenting an average deviation of 6 % from the published PEM model from Ref. study A and an average of 5 % deviation from the Ref. study B model.

The fuel cell stack can be approached as a solid block that produces heat and electricity. Assuming that the temperature for the whole fuel cell stack is uniformly distributed, no temperature variation occurs at the membrane electrolyte layer. Considering the thermal balance of the fuel stack, the thermal energy consists of the input gas enthalpy, output gas enthalpy, reaction enthalpy, and electrical power [43]. The chemical reaction can produce the output electricity (P_{el}), which will reduce the total thermal energy. The fuel cell (FC) can convert into electricity only a fraction of the internal energy contained in the hydrogen, while the remaining energy is either dissipated or absorbed by the system, causing an increase in the operating temperature [44]. Based on the thermal energy balance applied to the FC, the following equation is obtained:

$$Q_n = Q_{gen} - Q_c \quad (43)$$

where:

- Q_{gen} = heating power generated (W)
- Q_e = heating power dissipated (W)
- Q_n = internal heating power acquired by system (W)

However, the fuel cell's generated heat is given due to the balance of the heating power released by the chemical reaction (Q_c), the generated electrical power (P_{el}) and the heating power related to the sensible and latent heat ($Q_{la,se}$) of the reactants and the reaction product by the following equation [44,45]:

$$Q_{gen} = Q_c - P_{el} - Q_{la,se} \quad (44)$$

The theoretical power due to chemical reaction (Q_c) depends on the higher heating value of the hydrogen fuel, $HHV_{H_2} = 285.55$ kJ/mol, and the consumption rate of hydrogen, $n_{H_2,cons}$, given by:

$$Q_c = HHV_{H_2} \cdot n_{H_2,cons} \quad (45)$$

At this point, it is useful to mention that the consumption rate of hydrogen, $n_{H_2,cons}$, and oxygen $n_{O_2,cons}$, as well as the generation rate of water, $n_{H_2O,gen}$, are given by the number of fuel cells and the stack current:

$$n_{H_2,cons} = N_{cell} \cdot \frac{I}{2F} \quad (46)$$

$$n_{O_2,cons} = N_{cell} \cdot \frac{I}{4F} \quad (47)$$

$$n_{H_2O,gen} = N_{cell} \cdot \frac{I}{2F} \quad (48)$$

However, to avoid membrane degradation and failure in the fuel cell, the reactant flow rate at the inlet of the fuel cell must be equal to or higher than the consuming rate of the reactant [35]. For this reason, the stoichiometric rate is linked to the reactant molar flow rate by the following equations:

$$n_{H_2} = \lambda_{H_2} \cdot n_{H_2,cons} \quad (49)$$

$$\dot{n}_{O_2} = \lambda_{O_2} \cdot \dot{n}_{O_2,cons} \quad (50)$$

The latent and sensible heating, $Q_{la,se}$, for a PEM fuel stack, can be estimated by the following equation [44,45]:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{la,se} = & C_{p,H_2} \cdot (\dot{n}_{H_2,out} \cdot T_{fc} - \dot{n}_{H_2,in} \cdot T_{in}) + C_{p,O_2} \cdot (\dot{n}_{O_2,out} \cdot T_{fc} - \dot{n}_{O_2,in} \cdot T_{in}) \\ & + C_{p,N_2} \cdot (\dot{n}_{N_2,out} \cdot T_{fc} - \dot{n}_{N_2,in} \cdot T_{amb}) + C_{p,H_2O} \cdot \dot{n}_{H_2O,gen} \cdot (T_{fc} - T_{amb}) \\ & + \dot{n}_{H_2O,gen} \cdot H_{v,H_2O} \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

Where H_{v,H_2O} is the latent heat of water evaporation ($H_{v,H_2O} = 2.260$ J/kg at 25 °C and 1 bar) and C_{p,H_2} , C_{p,O_2} , C_{p,N_2} and C_{p,H_2O} are the specific heat capacities of hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, and water respectively. For simplicity purposes of the steady state PEMFC model, the inlet temperature T_{in} is assumed equal to the fuel cell temperature T_{fc} . Moreover, it is important to present the molar flow rate balance for the reactants and the products of the electrochemical process:

$$\dot{n}_{H_2,in} = \lambda_{H_2} \cdot \dot{n}_{H_2,cons} \quad (52)$$

$$\dot{n}_{H_2,out} = \dot{n}_{H_2,in} - \dot{n}_{H_2,cons} \quad (53)$$

$$\dot{n}_{O_2,in} = \lambda_{O_2} \cdot \dot{n}_{O_2,cons} \quad (54)$$

$$\dot{n}_{O_2,out} = \dot{n}_{O_2,in} - \dot{n}_{O_2,cons} \quad (55)$$

$$\dot{n}_{N_2,in} = \dot{n}_{O_2,in} \cdot \frac{0.79}{0.21} \quad (56)$$

$$\dot{n}_{N_2,out} = \dot{n}_{N_2,in} - \dot{n}_{N_2,cons} \quad (57)$$

The total generated power that is obtained from the fuel stack is given by Ref. [36]:

$$P_{el} = I \cdot V_{fc} \cdot N_{cell} \quad (58)$$

Finally, the dissipated heating power is defined as the product of the difference between the FC operating temperature, T_{fc} , and the ambient temperature, T_{amb} , and the heat transfer coefficient, H_t and [46]:

$$Q_c = H_t \cdot (T_{fc} - T_{amb}) \quad (59)$$

Thus, the overall thermal efficiency of the PEM is given by the following equation [36]:

$$\eta_{fc} = \frac{Q_c}{P_{el}} = \frac{I \cdot V_{fc} \cdot N_{cell}}{HHV_{H_2} \cdot \dot{n}_{H_2,cons}} \quad (60)$$

Fig. S3 in the Supplementary Material shows the generated PEMFC's heat and the overall thermal efficiency, η_{FC} . It also shows the drop in the PEM thermal efficiency due to the increasing generated and internal electrochemical heat and the respective decrease of the fuel cell's voltage, V_{fc} . Moreover, the sum of sensible and latent heat has a slight effect on the generated heat and for this reason, it is usually considered neglected by PEM thermal models.

2.4. Metal hydride tank modeling

Hydrogen storage technology utilizing metal hydride tanks operates on the principle of dissociative chemisorption, where hydrogen gas is absorbed and chemically bonded to the surface of a porous metal material. This chemical bonding within the metal hydride substantially lowers the potential risks associated with the storage system. A key benefit of this technology is its superior volumetric density, allowing metal hydride storage tanks to be much more compact compared to other storage options, such as high-pressure systems. This technical characteristic facilitates easier integration and installation in various applications without requiring extensive safety clearances by high-pressure systems. Furthermore, metal hydride tanks can operate at lower pressures, enhancing safety and potentially reducing the energy

consumption associated with the compression of hydrogen, offering a more efficient and environmentally friendly storage solution.

In the present hydrogen storage system modeling, an analytical model of the GKN Hydrogen (i.e., model HY2MEDI) [26] was developed to work efficiently with the connected electrolyzer and PEM fuel cell. The metal hydride tank consists of TiFe-based alloy and has a maximum storage and electricity capacity of 120 kg hydrogen and 4 kWh. The TiFe-based alloy used in the examined model offers low enthalpy requirements and environmental sustainability, showcasing a perfectly matched choice for hydrogen storage. Its moderate reaction enthalpy enables efficient hydrogen absorption and release under manageable thermal and pressure conditions, aligning seamlessly with the model's goals for practical and secure energy storage solutions. More than 95 % of the hydrogen is chemically bonded within the metal hydride. The system operates under a maximum pressure of about 35 bars, equivalent to the output pressure of the electrolyzer, classifying it as a low-pressure system. A heat management system preheats the tank to discharge the metal hydride storage tank and supply the released hydrogen to the fuel cell. The operation of the metal hydride tank will be illustrated in the next section, showcasing its storage capacity levels over a year for the demo building.

2.5. Battery system modeling

The battery storage system consists of Lead-acid batteries, and the main component has been exploited from the Modelica open-source BuildingSystems library through the Dymola environment [47]. The specific battery technology has been selected as it is considered the most mature, reliable, and widespread technology for electricity energy storage for both residential and industrial sectors [48]. The examined Dymola-based model has been adopted from the validated model of Rotas et al. [49], defining the state of charge (SOC) in relation to the total capacity of batteries:

$$SOC(t) = SOC(t_0) - \left(\frac{1}{C_{bat}} \right) \cdot \int I(t) dt \quad (61)$$

The nominal capacity of the chosen 12 V Lead-acid is 2.88 kWh, and the minimum SOC is selected at 10 % to enhance battery lifetime and reduce the degradation rate. Moreover, the battery model avoided over-discharging and overcharging to prevent a significant reduction in its lifespan [50]. The lifetime of the battery system is calculated based on the dynamic rain flow counting method, analyzing how it is affected by the depths of discharge [51]. The number of batteries throughout the HRES model optimization fluctuates from 1 to 300, with an overall capacity of 2.88 kWh to 864 kWh.

2.6. Photovoltaic system modeling

The Photovoltaic system of the examined HRES model has been developed in the Dymola environment based on the Modelica open-source BuildingSystems library [47] and the respective model by Duffy et al. [52]. The design of the PV panels follows a digital-twin circuit of a two-diode model cell, and it has been validated by the INTEMA.building tool through the modeling and simulation studies of [49,53]. The installation of the PV panels is assumed to be placed on the top of the roof of a demo building in the city of Athens. Thus, the optimum tilted angle is 30° and the orientation is South (i.e., azimuth angle is 0°). The examined PV panel is designed by SHARP (NU-JD440 model) with a nominal maximum power of 440W, according to the technical characteristics of the manufacturer, as shown in Table 3 [54]. The selection of this PV panel was realized based on its high efficiency, technical characteristics, and validated modeling and simulation". The PV system output power fluctuates from 20 kW to 60 kW throughout the HRES model optimization, with a connected number of 46 panels (i.e., approximately 101 m² covered area) to 137 panels (i.e., approximately

Table 3
Technical characteristics of the PV modules according to the manufacturer under standard test conditions^a [54].

Parameters	Values	
Maximum power	P_{max}	440 W
Module efficiency	η_{Ref}	0.199
Open circuit voltage	V_{oc}	49.77 V
Short-circuit current	I_{sc}	11.49 a
Number of cells	n_{cells}	2 strings of 72 cells in series
Panel surface (type)	A_{field}	2.108 m × 1.048 m (SharpNU-JD440)
Tilted angle	β	30°
Azimuth angle	γ	0° (South)

^a Solar irradiance of 1000 W/m² and ambient temperature of 25 °C.

303 m² covered area).

2.7. Followed methodology

The design and the development of the examined hydrogen storage model are conducted in the Dymola environment through the utilization of the INTEMA.building tool written in the programming language Modelica [53,55]. Furthermore, each component is examined as a white-box model [56] based on each energy behavior and physical principles (i.e., energy balance, mass balance, etc.) extensively analyzed in the above-mentioned Sections 2.1 to 2.5.

At first, a parametric analysis takes place to provide a reasonable range for the examined variables, aiming to set valuable insights for the optimization of the model’s function. For the parametric analysis, the parametric variables are the number of batteries of the connected battery system and the capacity of the MH tank in hydrogen (kg), while the respective parameter is the PV system’s maximum power, as shown in Table 4.

The parametric investigation was examined on the basis of the model’s total cost (€) and the demanded grid electricity (kWh). For the present study, the total cost is defined as the sum of all components’ capital costs, $C_{cap, total}$, which were considered through extensive grey literature and literature review on HRES and the sum of the operational cost, $C_{oper, total}$, which reflects the cost of the grid electricity, as it is depicted on Table 5 and according to the following equations:

$$C_{Cap, total} = C_{MHtank} + C_{PEMFC} + C_{Electrolyzer} + C_{PVs} + C_{BatterySystem} \quad (62)$$

$$C_{BatterySystem} = C_{Batteries} + C_{Batteries} \cdot (1 + r)^{\frac{N}{2}} \quad (63)$$

$$C_{oper, total} = C_{Grid} \cdot RIR \quad (64)$$

It is worth mentioning that the capital costs of each component (see Table 5) include the costs of various subsystems (i.e., cables, controllers, pumps, etc.) that are needed for the efficient function of the hydrogen system per se. Moreover, the electricity price for the connected grid in Greece is set to 0.20 €/kWh_{el} [57] and the respective real interest rate, RIR, for an inflation rate, r of 3 % and an examined period, N of 25 years is given from the following formula [58]:

$$RIR = \frac{(1 + r)^N - 1}{(1 + r)^N \cdot r} \quad (65)$$

The total cost at the present time is calculated as below:

$$C_{total} = C_{Cap, total} + C_{oper, total} \quad (66)$$

Table 4
 Parametric variables and parameters for the examined hydrogen storage model.

Name	Type	Range
Number of batteries	Variable	[0, 300]
MH tank capacity [kg]	Variable	[0, 200]
PV system nominal power [kW]	Parameter	[20,60]

Table 5
 The total capital cost of the examined hydrogen storage system’s components.

Component	Capital Cost	Reference Study
Metal hydride tank	2000 €/kg	[10,57–59]
PEM fuel cell	1300 €/kW	[60–62]
Electrolyzer	1400 €/kW	[58,62,63]
PV panels	300 €/panel	[54]
Batteries	250 €/kWh	[64,65]
Grid electricity	0.20 €/kWh _{el}	[66]

After the parametric analysis, the optimization process of the hydrogen storage system is taking place with core criteria the minimization of the total cost and the dependency on the grid. For this reason, the examined objective functions F_1 and F_2 are defined as:

$$F_1 = C_{total} [€] \quad (67)$$

$$F_2 = E_{grid} [kWh] \quad (68)$$

The optimization model was developed in the Python programming language based on the multi-objective optimization Pymoo library [59], while the examined model was simulated in the Dymola environment for a year and an hourly simulation step through the DASSL solver. Thus, the coupling of Modelica and Python programming languages is necessary, and it can be achieved through various methods, such as the functional mock-up interface (FMI), utilizing interface libraries, or accessing directly the translated executable file Dymosim. In the present research, the examined model is developed with the Dymosim method because it minimizes computational costs, which is crucial when a huge number of evaluations is required.

Dynamic model simulator (i.e., Dymosim) is a Modelica-based simulation tool that includes the machine code necessary for model simulation. The Dymosim method uses the Dymola environment to generate and export a translated modelica-written model as an executable file, called dymosim.exe. The executable file receives the simulation parameters from the input file “dsin.txt”, and after the successful run, the simulation results are stored in the “dsres.mat” file and the respective simulation statistics at the “dslog.txt”. This format offers the advantage of compiling dymosim without any graphical interface, providing essential functionality for initiating simulations and thereby avoiding the computational overhead introduced by the graphical user interface. Moreover, dymosim is flexible and robust as it can be used through high performant solvers without extra cost making with different operating modes.

Thus, a Dymola-Python interface module is developed on a Python script that runs the dymosim.exe file and loads its simulation outcome. First, the model’s fundamental variables (i.e., MH tank capacity and number of batteries) and simulation parameters (i.e., number of PV panels) are set on the input file of “dsin.txt” to be accessible by Dymosim. The interface conducts the simulation by calling the “dymosim.exe” executable and, after the simulation, extracts the calculated variables of interest from the generated “dsres.mat” file. These variables are used to evaluate the objective function. The process is then repeated for the subsequent iterations.

In the present study, the non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (NGASS-II) from the Pymoo library was utilized to minimize the multi-objective problem, and the Pareto-front was used to provide the optimum pair of variables among a set of optimum solutions. The NSGA-II algorithm was selected due to its efficiency in solving complex and non-linear problems which address conflicting objectives, such as the present minimization of the total capital cost and grid electricity demand. A sensitivity analysis among relative algorithms (e.g., Particle Swarm Optimization, Differential Evolution, and Genetic Algorithm) showed superior convergence and diversity maintenance for the NSGA-II algorithm. Additionally, its flexible and robust processing of a high number of design scenarios throughout its interaction with the

Table 6
NSGA-II optimization criteria.

NSGA-II Optimization Criteria	Values
Population size	60
Number of offsprings	30
Sampling method	FloatRandomSampling
Crossover operator (Crossover probability, distribution index)	(0.95, 20)
Mutation operator	20

developed Dymola-Python interface.

Table 6 illustrates the NSGA-II optimization criteria. Respectively, the augmented scalarization function (ASF) was applied to approach the Pareto front by weighing the convergence and diversity. ASF is a scalarization technique that locates the non-dominated solutions as the best trade-offs among the conflicting objectives [[59]].

3. Results and discussion

In the present section, a detailed investigation of its optimum operation will take place after the development and validation of the HRES with a hydrogen storage system and each component of it in the Dymola

Fig. 3. (a) Total cost and (b) Grid electricity as a function of the number of batteries for 50 kg, 100 kg, and 200 kg of H₂ MH Tank and (c) Total cost and (d) Grid electricity as a function of the capacity of MH Tank for 100, 200, and 300 number of batteries for the PV system of 20 kW.

environment. First, a parametric analysis for three different PV systems (i.e., 20 kW, 40 kW, and 60 kW) investigates the number of batteries and the MH tank capacity as variables, providing useful insights for the optimization settings. Then, a coupling of the Dymola model to Python due to the Pymoo library optimizes the hydrogen storage system, utilizing the Pareto method for five PV systems (i.e., from 20 kW to 60 kW). Finally, an investigation of the optimum Pareto solution leads to the optimum design of the present model in terms of minimum total cost and dependency on the electricity grid.

3.1. Parametric analysis

The HRES model with hydrogen storage system was tested for the yearly weather data for the city of Athens, obtained from the PV-GIS

database [[60]]. Thus, the examined model is simulated in the Dymola environment (See Fig. 1 for the outline of the model in Dymola) for a time period of a year with the Dassl algorithm and an hourly step. Every component was developed and simulated using the Modelica language, and it underwent testing to confirm that its nominal capacities and outputs align with the specifications provided by the manufacturers, as provided in Section 2. Some of the main model’s parameters are shown in Table 2.

The aim of the model’s simulation is the parametric analysis for a set of variables, using the number of PV panels as a parameter. Specifically, a number of batteries (i.e., 100, 200, and 300 batteries) and three capacities of the MH Tank (i.e., 50 kg, 100 kg, and 200 kg) are tested for the PV systems of 20 kW, 40 kW, and 60 kW in terms of the model’s total cost (€) and demanded grid electricity (kWh). It is important to notice

Fig. 4. (a) Total cost and (b) Grid electricity as a function of the number of batteries for 50 kg, 100 kg, and 200 kg of H₂ MH Tank and (c) Total cost and (d) Grid electricity as a function of the capacity of MH Tank for 100, 200, and 300 number of batteries for the PV system of 40 kW.

Fig. 5. (a) Total Cost and (b) Grid electricity as a function of the number of batteries for 50 kg, 100 kg, and 200 kg of H₂ MH Tank and (c) Total cost and (d) Grid electricity as a function of the capacity of MH Tank for 100, 200, and 300 number of batteries for the PV system of 60 kW.

(as mentioned in Section 2.1) that the battery system has priority for the charge and discharge process compared to the electrolyzer. The results from the parametric analysis for the three PV systems are shown in Figs. 3–5.

For the PV system of 20 kW and the MH tank capacity as a parameter (Fig. 3a and b) the minimum range for the three selected MH tank capacities is 20–30 batteries (i.e., 57.6 kWh – 86.4 kWh nominal capacity) for both the total system’s cost and the dependent electricity from the grid. Of course, the total cost is higher as larger MH tank is installed, but this does not affect the system’s energy autonomy which reaches the minimum value of around 62%. This occurs, as the 20 kW PV system cannot produce enough electricity to support both the battery system and the electrolyzer, so the hydrogen storage system peaks its energy autonomy from the grid. Moreover, it is obvious from Fig. 3c and d, that there are no improvements on the two objective functions for 100, 200, and 300 batteries for the different MH tank capacities.

Increasing the maximum power of the PV system from 20 kW to 40 kW (i.e., from 46 to 91 PV panels) the optimum number of batteries (Fig. 4a and b) slightly increases to 30–50 batteries, while the best performance is noticed for the 50 kg MH tank, as the 1–3% difference on

the energy autonomy is considered insignificant compared to the total cost gap among the 100 kg and 200 kg tanks. For the case Fig. 4c and d, the minimum demanded grid electricity of 2300 kWh is noted for the 300 batteries and 95 kg tank, while an energy autonomy of 86%–88% is achieved for over 100 kg tanks for the three battery systems. Clearly, the system’s total cost has a linear dependency on the number of batteries and MH tank capacities.

Finally, it is interesting to analyze the model performance with the integrated 60 kW PV system, in which 100% energy autonomy is achieved for the 100 kg and 200 kg MH tanks for the whole spectrum of the number of batteries (Fig. 5b). However, similar performance showcases the 50 kg tank, as it manages 98.2% energy autonomy with a peak of 99.2% for a stack of 25 batteries. Exactly the same pattern in terms of grid electricity occurs in the case of 100 batteries and a variable number of tank capacities with a peak at 25 kg tank (Fig. 5d). The total cost of both cases of the parametric investigation for the 50 kg tank (Fig. 5a) and the 100 number of batteries (Fig. 5c) increases dramatically over the respective parametric variable as the electricity cost is set to zero for the comparative parameter.

An explanatory summary of the parametric analysis is given in

Fig. 6. (a) Energy Autonomy (%) per number of batteries for a MH tank capacity of 100 kg for the PV systems of 20 kW, 40 kW, and 60 kW, respectively and (b) Energy Autonomy (%) per MH tank capacity (kg) for the stack of 200 batteries for the PV systems of 20 kW, 40 kW, and 60 kW, respectively.

Fig. 6a and b, where a median case of a 100 kg MH tank and a 200 battery system is examined for their energy autonomy related to the number of batteries and different capacities of the MH tank, respectively.

Overall, the parametric analysis explored variables such as the number of lead-acid batteries, PV panels and MH tank capacity. It is important to mention that the above-mentioned boundary conditions were chosen to reflect realistic operational ranges for residential or small commercial applications. Thus, the range of parameters were selected based on practical constraints, such as roof space for PV panels, typical battery sizes available in the market, and the scalability of MH tanks for integration within HRES as well as to reflect the examined building’s electricity load demand.

3.2. Hybrid storage system optimization

The parametric analysis provided the fundamental basis for configuring the optimization parameters and criteria. The Dymola – Python interface through the Dymosim method resulted in the optimum Pareto fronts for the different PV systems from 20 kW to 60 kW, as depicted in Table 7 and Fig. 7. The optimization process has occurred with the Non-

Table 7
Optimum Pareto solutions for the examined PV systems.

PV capacity	Number of batteries	H ₂ capacity MH tank	Total cost	Grid electrical energy	Energy autonomy
[kW]	[–]	[kg]	[€]	[kWh]	[%]
20	160	0.00	240,711	20,660	70.3
30	149	60.55	312,231	7,805	88.8
40	142	60.16	299,139	3,621	98.8
50	203	9.93	234,016	1,140	98.4
60	118	4.00	175,059	581	99.2

Fig. 7. Total costs, battery system, MH Tank, and electricity grid cost for the optimum Pareto solutions of the different PV systems.

dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II) for the selected range of optimization variables, as shown in Table 4 and the algorithm minimization criteria, as showcased in Table 6. Moreover, the Energy Autonomy fraction (%) was calculated to indicate the system’s energy autonomy from the grid.

For the PV system of 20 kW, it is evident that the surplus of electricity is inadequate to feed both the battery system and the electrolyzer. Thus, the optimum Pareto front provides a stack of 160 batteries with no MH tank at all, as the model prioritizes the battery system and there is no amount of electricity to support the electrolyzer to generate H₂ for the MH tank. This leads to a total cost of 240,711 € and a respective energy autonomy of 70.3 %. For the PV systems of 30 kW and 40 kW, the optimum solutions for both battery and hydrogen storage systems are similar with a difference of 10 % in energy autonomy due to the 10-kW difference in PVs maximum power. It is interesting to notice that the MH tank capacity peaks at 61 kg (i.e., 30 kW and 40 kW PV system) as the number of PVs increases, while the maximum energy autonomy of 99.2 % is noted for a 4 kg MH tank. Similarly, the number of batteries peaks at the 50 kW PV system and then declines with the optimum battery system of 118 lead-acid batteries.

The optimum Pareto front solutions over the examined PV systems showcase the linear dependency of the photovoltaic panel’s maximum power to the system’s energy autonomy, with the maximum EA fraction of 99.2 % for the 60 kW PV system (See Fig. 8). Thus, the optimum design solution among the examined Pareto solutions, as shown in Fig. 9a, is the stack of 118 batteries and the MH tank of 4 kg capacity for the PV system of 60 kW. Moreover, the Pareto-front for the selected PV system is illustrated in Fig. 9b.

However, it is interesting to mention that even if the optimum Pareto solution is considered for the 60 kW PV system, the MH tank is operational only for the 30 kW and 40 kW PV system, as shown in Fig. 10a. This occurs as over 50 kW of installed PV power, the examined model is

Fig. 8. Demanded electricity from the grid and the respective energy autonomy fraction for the optimum Pareto solutions of the different PV systems.

Fig. 9. Optimum Pareto solutions in terms of total cost and energy autonomy for the examined PV systems, and (b) Pareto Front for the PV system of 60 kW.

Fig. 10. (a) The MH tank capacities and (b) the energy autonomy of the optimum Pareto solutions over time for the five examined PV systems for a year.

fully covered by the produced photovoltaic energy and the integrated battery system. Similarly, due to high capital costs and a deficit of electricity in the controller, the MH tank does not contribute to the hybrid storage model below 30 kW of installed PV power. In addition, as illustrated in Fig. 10a the PV system for the installed capacity of 30–40 kW (i.e., the range in which the MH tank is functional) determines the number of months that the MH tank will be full. This is obvious during the summer period, with the MH tank of 30 kW PV being full for a total

of 3 months and the respective tank of 40 kW for a total of 6 months. Fig. 10b validates this observation as it showcases the increasing rate of reaching the maximum energy autonomy as the installed PV power increases.

3.3. Optimum design investigation and discussion

The multi-objective optimization for the examined PV systems resulted in the optimum design of all the tested Pareto-front solutions as the hybrid storage system of 118 lead-acid stacks of batteries and an MH tank of 4 kg capacity. Moreover, the developed control system model

Fig. 11. The SOC of the optimum MH tank and battery system for the (a) PV system of 60 kW and (b) PV system of 40 kW.

was designed to prioritize the battery system in both charging and discharging daily profiles and then to the electrolyzer for feeding the metal hydride tank. If both are above the 100 % SOC, then the PV panels' power surplus is fed back to the grid. Fig. 11a demonstrates both the MH tank and the battery system SOC for a year. It is obvious that the full capacity of the battery system is utilized during the winter period when the PVs cannot fully cover the electrical load. For the same reason, the MH tank's charging is realized slowly, as the full capacity is reached after January. Respectively, during the summer period, when the battery system's SOC ranges from 70 % to 100 %, the electrical load is fully covered, and the MH tank is not working. Though, it stands as an alternative energy storage source, improving the energy security of the system as a whole.

However, it is useful to provide the SOC of the MH tank and batteries for the medium optimal solution of Pareto-front solutions for the 40 kW PV system, in which the MH tank is fully operational, as shown in Fig. 11b. For this case, the battery system fluctuates from 20 % to 50 % during the winter period, extending the full charging period of the MH tank to 2–3 months as the system absorbs H₂ to feed the PEM fuel cell in the meantime. Finally, it is fully discharged after 2–3 months after August when the system cannot fully be supported by the battery system. Although the 40 kW system reaches an energy autonomy of 98.8 %, the total capital cost is doubled compared to the optimal design of the 60 kW system, with a total cost of 299,139 €.

Moreover, Fig. 12 shows the surplus electrical power provided by PV panels to the grid and the respective demanded electrical power from the grid. It is obvious that there is a great surplus during the summer with a total of 38,612 kWh produced, while in the winter period, the system cannot cover its needs without the grid input, which reaches a total of 581 kWh. This operation offers promising benefits from its connection to the grid through net metering or net billing payback frameworks.

4. Conclusions

The emergence and scaling-up of hybrid renewable energy systems due to the intense energy transition for an energy-sustainable future pose numerous challenges to energy supply reliability and security. Thus, the research and integration of energy storage systems in HRES are crucial for the overthrow of conventional unsustainable energy systems due to improved performance and consistency. Among the developing energy storage technologies, metal hydride tanks emerge as a promising alternative technology, providing high energy density and long-term storage capabilities. In the present study, a novel hydrogen storage system with an integrated MH tank was developed to cover the electrical load of 1000 m², located in the city of Athens. The hydrogen storage system was modeled and simulated in the Dymola environment for a period of the year. The examined model is supplied electricity from a PV system which covers the demanded building electrical load and then

supplies the surplus energy to the hybrid storage system, prioritizing the integrated battery system.

In order to design the optimum hydrogen storage system in terms of total capital cost and dependency on the grid electricity, a parametric analysis was conducted for different PV systems from 20 kW to 60 kW. The analysis investigated the simulation of the parametric variables of 100, 200, and 300 stacks of lead-acid batteries and of 50, 100, and 200 kg MH tank capacity for the different numbers of photovoltaic panels. It resulted that for the integrated 60 kW PV system, a 100 % energy autonomy is achieved for the 100 kg and 200 kg MH tanks for the whole spectrum of number of batteries, while similar performance was noticed for the 50 kg tank, as it manages 98.2 % energy autonomy with a peak of 99.2 % for a stack of 25 batteries.

The mapping of design parametric variables led to the final multi-objective optimization of the hydrogen storage system through an in-house Dymola-Python interface. The objective functions were to set the model's total cost and the demanded grid electricity, and the optimum solutions were selected with the Pareto-front for the examined PV systems. Among them, the optimum Pareto solution was for the installation of a 118 stack of batteries connected to a 4 kg MH tank, performing 100 % energy autonomy from the grid. It is interesting that even though the PV systems of 40 kW and 50 kW provide a similar energy autonomy of around 98 %, the total cost is doubled compared to the optimum of 60 kW. This occurs, as lower maximum power from the PV system results in higher MH tank capacities to support the battery system, outperforming the MH tank's total cost. Thus, even though the integration of MH tanks into hybrid renewable energy systems is critical for their viability and grid autonomy, the optimization of their performance and cost within the system as a whole, is necessary for their establishment in the research field and market as well.

Overall, this study provides a novel integration of a metal hydride (MH) hydrogen storage system within a hybrid renewable energy framework in a typical residential building, achieving significant energy autonomy. Specifically, the multi-objective optimization through the developed Dymola-Python connection demonstrates a cost-effective design achieving 99.2 % energy independence, notably outperforming conventional systems. Moreover, the research raises interest in the impact of building design limitations on the respective HRES design in terms of the functionality and cost-effectiveness of the MH tank as an auxiliary energy storage system. Except for the design boundaries, several limitations can be observed by transferring the presented simulated hydrogen storage system into real-life applications. Specifically, there are a variety of inconsistencies, such as the variable real-time energy demand, unpredicted degradation and damage of the installed energy system, and unforeseen weather conditions leading to variant PV output. Additionally, focusing on the transition of the simplistic MH tank model to real-world use, factors like the ideal energy efficiency and control system, thermal losses, kinetic and thermodynamic interactions, and component aging are overlooked, providing an opportunity for future experimental testing and validation.

However, for future research, it is worth investigating the boundary parameters (i.e., technical and physical limitations) of a residential or commercial building, which will reevaluate the multi-objective optimization configurations. Likewise, it is interesting to investigate a detailed MH tank model to bridge the gap between simulation and real-life application by incorporating degradation and uncertainty modeling and capturing the effect of the thermal and kinetic behaviour under dynamic operational conditions. Furthermore, it would be noteworthy to research the diversification of the examined optimized hydrogen storage system, integrating other sustainable energy technologies and features, like geothermal heat pumps, wind turbines, and passive design of the building space. Finally, for future research, it could be interesting to explore the integration of electrical loads other than the appliances and lighting system through the integration of heat pumps, electric vehicles, etc.

Fig. 12. The electrical power provided by PV panels to the grid (i.e., in case of full batteries and storage tank) and the respective demanded electrical power from the grid.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nikolaos Ziozas: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Petros Iliadis:** Supervision, Software, Methodology. **Evangelos Bellos:** Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Angeliki Kitsopoulou:** Writing – review & editing. **Renos Rotas:** Writing – review & editing. **Dimitra Gonidaki:** Writing – review & editing. **Nikolaos Nikolopoulos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work has been carried out in the framework of the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101103450 (Renewable Energy-based Positive Homes – RENplusHOMES).

Nomenclature

A	Area, m ²
C	Concentration, mol/cm ³
C _{bat}	Capacity of batteries
C _{Batteries}	Batteries cost, €/kWh
C _{BatterySystem}	Total battery system cost, €/kWh
C _{Cap, total}	Total capital cost, €
C _{Electrolyzer}	Electrolyzer cost, €/kWh
C _{Grid}	Grid electricity cost, €/kWh
C _{MHtank}	Metal Hydride Tank cost, €/kg
C _{oper}	Operational cost, €
C _{PVs}	PV panels cost, €/panel
C _{PEMFC}	PEM fuel cell cost, €/kW
C _p	Specific heat capacity, J/kg•K
E _o	Open circuit voltage, V
F	Faraday constant, s•A/mol
HHV	Higher heating value, kJ/mol
H _t	Heat transfer coefficient, W/K
H _v	Latent heat of evaporation, J/kg
i	Current density, A/m ²
i _L	Maximum current density, A/m ²
I	Current, A
I _{SC}	Short-circuit current, A
J	Current density, A/m ²
L	Thickness, m
m	Mass flow rate, kg/s
M	Molar mass, kg/mol
LHV	Lower Heating Value, kJ/mol
N _{cell}	Number of series-connected electrolytic cells, - n Molar flow rate, mol/A•s
n _{cons}	Consumption rate, mol/A•s
n _{gen}	Generation rate, mol/A•s
P	Pressure, atm
P _{el}	Electrical power, W
Q _e	Heating power dissipated, W
Q _{gen}	Heating power generated, W
Q _{heat}	Heat thermal losses, W
Q _{la,se}	Heating power related to the sensible and latent heat, W
Q _n	Internal heating power acquired by the system, W
Q _{fuel}	Power produced, W.

R _m	Membrane resistance, Ω
R _c	Resistance of the constant part of the cell, Ω
R _{PEM}	Ohmic resistance, Ω
r	Inflation rate, %
r _{mem}	Specific membrane resistance
R	Gas constant, J/mol•K
T	Temperature, K
U _{tn}	Thermoneutral cell voltage, V
V	Potential, V
V _{act}	Activation overpotential, V
V _{con}	Concentration overpotential, V
V _o	Reversible potential, V
V _{oc}	Open circuit voltage, V
V _{ohm}	Ohmic overpotential, V
W _{max,fc}	Maximum electrical total work of the fuel cell, W
x	Molar fraction, mole/mole

Greek Symbols

ΔG	Gibbs free energy, J
ΔH	Theoretical energy demand, J
β	Tilted angle, °
γ	Azimuth angle, °
η	Efficiency, %
λ	Stoichiometric rate
ξ	Parametric coefficients, - ‘
σ	Local ionic conductivity, S/m
Ψ	Membrane Hydration, -

Subscripts & Superscripts

an	Anode
ca	Cathode
con	Consumption
fc	Fuel cells
gen	Generation
H ₂	Hydrogen
H ₂ O	Water
N ₂	Nitrogen in the air stream
O ₂	Oxygen
PEM	Proton exchange membrane

Abbreviations

ASF	Augmented Scalarization Function
HRES	Hybrid Renewable Energy System
HESS	Hydrogen Energy Storage System
MEL	Membrane Electrolyte Layer
MH	Metal Hydride
MHT	Metal Hydride Tank
PEMFC	Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RIR	Real Interest Rate
RMCR	Radiation Mini-Channel Reactor
SOC	State Of Charge

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2025.04.522>.

References

- [1] Ziozas N, Tsoutsos T. Clean energy transition in Southeast Europe: the paradigm of Greece from a fossil fuel mediator to a community energy hub. In: Coenen FHJM, Hoppe T, editors. Renewable energy communities and the low carbon energy transition in Europe. Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2021. p. 75–95. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-84440-0_4.

- [2] Kilic M, Altun AF. Dynamic modelling and multi-objective optimization of off-grid hybrid energy systems by using battery or hydrogen storage for different climates. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* Jul. 2023;48(60):22834–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.12.103>.
- [3] Becherif M, Ramadan HS, Cabaret K, Picard F, Simoncini N, Bethoux O. Hydrogen energy storage: new techno-economic emergence solution analysis. *Energy Proc* Aug. 2015;74:371–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2015.07.629>.
- [4] Iversen Z, Achuthan A, Marzocca P, Aidun D. Optimal design of hybrid renewable energy systems (HRES) using hydrogen storage technology for data center applications. *Renew Energy Apr.* 2013;52:79–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2012.10.038>.
- [5] Wang Y, et al. Dynamic analysis and control optimization of hydrogen supply for the proton exchange membrane fuel cell and metal hydride coupling system with a hydrogen buffer tank. *Energy Convers Manag Sep.* 2023;291:117339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2023.117339>.
- [6] Yuan X, et al. Carbon footprint and embodied carbon transfer at the provincial level of the Yellow River Basin. *Sci Total Environ Jan.* 2022;803:149993. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.149993>.
- [7] Chabane D, et al. Coupling a metal hydride tank with a PEMFC for vehicular applications: a simulations framework. *Int J Energy Res Sep.* 2021;45(11):16511–23. <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.6898>.
- [8] Xu J, Zhang C, Wan Z, Chen X, Chan SH, Tu Z. Progress and perspectives of integrated thermal management systems in PEM fuel cell vehicles: a review. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev Mar.* 2022;155:111908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111908>.
- [9] Sakintuna B, Lamari-Darkrim F, Hirscher M. Metal hydride materials for solid hydrogen storage: a review. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Jun.* 2007;32(9):1121–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2006.11.022>.
- [10] Kumar K, Alam M, Rakshit D, Dutta V. Operational characteristics of metal hydride energy storage system in microgrid. *Energy Convers Manag May* 2019;187:176–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2019.03.019>.
- [11] Schlapbach L, Züttel A. Hydrogen-storage materials for mobile applications. *Nature Nov.* 2001;414(6861):353–8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35104634>.
- [12] Bellosta von Colbe J, et al. Application of hydrides in hydrogen storage and compression: achievements, outlook and perspectives. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Mar.* 2019;44(15):7780–808. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.01.104>.
- [13] Tolj I, Lototsky M, Parsons A, Pasupathi S. Fuel cell power pack with integrated metal hydride hydrogen storage for powering electric forklift. In: Kolhe M, Muhammad A, El Kharbachi A, Yuwono TY, editors. *Recent advances in renewable energy systems*. Singapore: Springer Nature; 2022. p. 19–27. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-1581-9_2.
- [14] Nguyen HQ, Shabani B. Review of metal hydride hydrogen storage thermal management for use in the fuel cell systems. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Sep.* 2021;46(62):31699–726. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.07.057>.
- [15] Davids W, et al. Metal hydride hydrogen storage tank for light fuel cell vehicle. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2019;44(Feb). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.01.227>.
- [16] Gambini M, Stilo T, Vellini M. Hydrogen storage systems for fuel cells: comparison between high and low-temperature metal hydrides. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Jun.* 2019;44(29):15118–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.04.083>.
- [17] Song C, et al. Using metal hydride H2 storage in mobile fuel cell equipment: design and predicted performance of a metal hydride fuel cell mobile light. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Sep.* 2014;39(27):14896–911. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2014.07.069>.
- [18] Tetuko AP, Shabani B, Andrews J. Thermal coupling of PEM fuel cell and metal hydride hydrogen storage using heat pipes. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Feb.* 2016;41(7):4264–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.12.194>.
- [19] Mellouli S, Askri F, Dhaou H, Jemni A, Ben Nasrallah S. A novel design of a heat exchanger for a metal-hydrogen reactor. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Oct.* 2007;32(15):3501–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2007.02.039>.
- [20] Wang D, et al. Design optimization and sensitivity analysis of the radiation mini-channel metal hydride reactor. *Energy Apr.* 2019;173:443–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2019.02.033>.
- [21] Kaplan Y. Effect of design parameters on enhancement of hydrogen charging in metal hydride reactors. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Mar.* 2009;34(5):2288–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2008.12.096>.
- [22] Di Giorgio P, Di Ilio G, Jannelli E, Conte FV. Numerical analysis of an energy storage system based on a metal hydride hydrogen tank and a lithium-ion battery pack for a plug-in fuel cell electric scooter. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Jan.* 2023;48(9):3552–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.10.205>.
- [23] Di Giorgio P, Di Ilio G, Scarpati G, Altomonte A, Jannelli E. Thermally integrated energy storage system for hybrid fuel cell electric bike: an experimental study. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Jun.* 2023;48(54):20914–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.10.043>.
- [24] Cho J-H, et al. Dynamic modeling and simulation of hydrogen supply capacity from a metal hydride tank. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Jul.* 2013;38(21):8813–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2013.02.142>.
- [25] Cavo M, Gadducci E, Rattazzi D, Rivarolo M, Magistri L. Dynamic analysis of PEM fuel cells and metal hydrides on a zero-emission ship: a model-based approach. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2021;46(Aug). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.07.104>.
- [26] "Hydrogen Storage," GKN Hydrogen. Accessed: May 28, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gknhydrogen.com/>.
- [27] AEM Electrolysers - Low-Cost Green Hydrogen," Enapter. Accessed: June 7, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.enapter.com/aem-electrolysers/>.
- [28] Ni M, Leung MKH, Leung DYC. Energy and exergy analysis of hydrogen production by a proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzer plant. *Energy Convers Manag Oct.* 2008;49(10):2748–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2008.03.018>.
- [29] Lykas P, Bellos E, Caralis G, Tzivanidis C. Dynamic investigation and optimization of a solar-based unit for power and green hydrogen production: a case study of the Greek island, kythnos. *Applied Sciences Nov.* 2022;12(21):11134. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app122111134>.
- [30] García-Valverde R, Espinosa N, Urbina A. Simple PEM water electrolyser model and experimental validation. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Jan.* 2012;37(2):1927–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2011.09.027>.
- [31] Ni M, Leung MKH, Leung DYC. *Electrochemistry modeling of proton exchange membrane (PEM) water electrolysis for hydrogen production*. 2006.
- [32] Ahmadi P, Dincer I, Rosen M. Development and assessment of an integrated biomass-based multi-generation energy system. *Energy Jul.* 2013;56:155–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2013.04.024>.
- [33] Gurau V, Barbir F, Liu H. An analytical solution of a half-cell model for PEM fuel cells. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society - J ELECTROCHEM SOC Jul.* 2000;147. <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.1393555>.
- [34] Ioroi T, Yasuda K, Siroma Z, Fujiwara N, Miyazaki Y. Thin film electrocatalyst layer for unitized regenerative polymer electrolyte fuel cells. *J Power Sources Nov.* 2002;112(2):583–7. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753\(02\)00466-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753(02)00466-4).
- [35] Ahmadi MH, et al. Thermodynamic analysis and optimization of a waste heat recovery system for proton exchange membrane fuel cell using transcritical carbon dioxide cycle and cold energy of liquefied natural gas. *J Nat Gas Sci Eng Aug.* 2016;34:428–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jngse.2016.07.014>.
- [36] Marandi S, Mohammadkhani F, Yari M. An efficient auxiliary power generation system for exploiting hydrogen boil-off gas (BOG) cold exergy based on PEM fuel cell and two-stage ORC: thermodynamic and exergoeconomic viewpoints. *Energy Convers Manag Sep.* 2019;195:502–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2019.05.018>.
- [37] Spiegel C. *PEM fuel cell modeling and simulation using Matlab*. Amsterdam : Boston: Academic Press/Elsevier; 2008.
- [38] Molaeianesh GR, Torabi F. *Fuel cell modeling and simulation: from microscale to macroscale*. Amsterdam Oxford Cambridge, MA: Elsevier; 2023.
- [39] Long R, Li B, Liu Z, Liu W. A hybrid system using a regenerative electrochemical cycle to harvest waste heat from the proton exchange membrane fuel cell. *Energy Dec.* 2015;93:2079–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2015.09.132>.
- [40] Miansari Me, Sedighi K, Amidpour M, Alizadeh E, Miansari Mo. Experimental and thermodynamic approach on proton exchange membrane fuel cell performance. *J Power Sources May* 2009;190(2):356–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2009.01.082>.
- [41] Chen P-C. The dynamics analysis and controller design for the PEM fuel cell under gas flowrate constraints. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Feb.* 2011;36(4):3110–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2010.11.106>.
- [42] Bigdeli N. *Optimal management of hybrid PV/fuel cell/battery power system: a comparison of optimal hybrid approaches*. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2015;42(C):377–93.
- [43] Xing Y. *Modeling and control strategies for a fuel cell system*. Springer Theses. Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-15112-5>.
- [44] San Martín I, Ursúa A, Sanchis P. Modelling of PEM fuel cell performance: steady-state and dynamic experimental validation. *Energies Feb.* 2014;7(2):670–700. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en7020670>.
- [45] Wang C, Nehrir MH, Shaw SR. Dynamic models and model validation for PEM fuel cells using electrical circuits. *IEEE Trans. On Energy Conversion Jun.* 2005;20(2):442–51. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEC.2004.8423257>.
- [46] Meng H. Numerical studies of liquid water behaviors in PEM fuel cell cathode considering transport across different porous layers. *Int J Hydrogen Energy Jun.* 2010;35(11):5569–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2010.03.073>.
- [47] BuildingSystems." Accessed: May 28, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://modelica-buildingsystems.de/>.
- [48] de Oliveira e Silva G, Hendrick P. Lead–acid batteries coupled with photovoltaics for increased electricity self-sufficiency in households. *Appl Energy Sep.* 2016;178:856–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.06.003>.
- [49] Rotas R, Iliadis P, Nikolopoulos N, Tomboulides A, Kosmatopoulos E. Dynamic simulation and performance enhancement analysis of a renewable driven trigeneration system. *Energies Jan.* 2022;15(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15103688>. Art. no. 10.
- [50] Coppitters D, De Paepe W, Contino F. Robust design optimization and stochastic performance analysis of a grid-connected photovoltaic system with battery storage and hydrogen storage. *Energy Dec.* 2020;213:118798. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.118798>.
- [51] Musallam M, Johnson CM. An efficient implementation of the rainflow counting algorithm for life consumption estimation. *IEEE Trans Reliab Sep.* 2012;61(4):978–86. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TR.2012.2221040>.
- [52] Duffie JA, Beckman WA, Blair N. *Solar engineering of thermal processes, photovoltaics and wind*. John Wiley & Sons; 2020.
- [53] Ziozas N, et al. Energy performance analysis of the renovation process in an Italian cultural heritage building. *Sustainability Jan.* 2024;16(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16072784>. Art. no. 7.
- [54] 440 Wp/Mono: NUJD440." Accessed: April. 23, 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://www.sharp.co.uk/440-wp-mono-nujd440>.
- [55] Bellos E, et al. Holistic renovation of a multi-family building in Greece based on dynamic simulation analysis. *J Clean Prod Dec.* 2022;381:135202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.135202>.

- [56] Li Y, O'Neill Z, Zhang L, Chen J, Im P, DeGraw J. Grey-box modeling and application for building energy simulations - A critical review 2021;146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111174>.
- [57] Danebergs J, Deledda S. Can hydrogen storage in metal hydrides be economically competitive with compressed and liquid hydrogen storage? A techno-economical perspective for the maritime sector. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* Jan. 2024;50:1040–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.08.313>.
- [58] Tribioli L, Cozzolino R. Techno-economic analysis of a stand-alone microgrid for a commercial building in eight different climate zones. *Energy Convers Manag* Jan. 2019;179:58–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2018.10.061>.
- [59] Hydrogen Tank." Accessed: June, 4, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://homerenergy.com/products/pro/docs/3.15/hydrogen_tank.html.
- [60] Cigolotti V, Genovese M. Stationary fuel cell applications: current and future technologies – costs, performances, and potential. Paris: Advanced Fuel Cells TCP. International Energy Agency; 2021.
- [61] Kamarudin SK, Wan Daud W, Som A Md, Takriff M, Mohammad A. Technical design and economic evaluation of a PEM fuel cell system. *J Power Sources* Jul. 2006;157:641–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2005.10.053>.
- [62] Hunter C, Penev M, Reznicek EP, Eichman J, Rustagi N, Baldwin SF. Techno-economic analysis of long-duration energy storage and flexible power generation technologies to support high variable renewable energy grids. Oct. 28, 2020, 3720769. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3720769>. Rochester, NY.
- [63] Krishnan S, et al. Present and future cost of alkaline and PEM electrolyser stacks. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* Oct. 2023;48(83):32313–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.05.031>.
- [64] Anuphappharadorn S, Sukchai S, Sirisamphanwong C, Ketjoy N. Comparison the economic analysis of the battery between lithium-ion and lead-acid in PV stand-alone application. *Energy Proc Dec.* 2014;56:352–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2014.07.167>.
- [65] Indra T, Geumpana T, Fattah IMR, Mahlia TMI. Techno-Economic analysis of hybrid diesel generators and renewable energy for a remote island in the Indian ocean using HOMER pro. *Sustainability* Aug. 2022;14:9846. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14169846>.
- [66] Bellos E, Tzivanidis C. Concentrating solar collectors for a trigeneration system—a comparative study. *Applied Sciences* Jan. 2020;10(13). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10134492>. Art. no. 13.
- [67] Georgousis N, Lykas P, Bellos E, Tzivanidis C. Multi-objective optimization of a solar-driven polygeneration system based on CO2 working fluid. *Energy Convers Manag* Jan. 2022;252:115136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2021.115136>.
- [68] Blank J, Deb K. Pymoo: multi-objective optimization in Python. *IEEE Access* 2020; 8:89497–509. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2990567>.
- [69] JRC Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS) - European Commission." Accessed: May 30, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pvg_tools/en/tools.html#TMY.